

Neutron Decay Constant Calculation Using Monte Carlo Method and Dynamic Mode Decomposition for Non-multiplying System

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ABSTRACT

The neutron decay constant α is a unique kinetic parameter that can be measured even in a non-multiplying system without nuclear fuel. Our previous study focused on the α value for the data assimilation to selectively improve only the thermal neutron scattering law (TSL) data for light water. However, since our previous studies used the deterministic method to calculate the α value, there is an issue to quantify the uncertainty due to the discretization in the deterministic method. To address this issue, this study aims to investigate the α calculation method using the Monte Carlo method for a water tank system. For this purpose, Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD) is applied to the kinetic calculation of OpenMC to extract the fundamental mode of the α value. By combining this method with the random sampling method, we also aim to quantify the statistical uncertainty of α as the uncertainty due to the analytical modeling method. The usefulness of DMD is investigated by comparing the estimated α value with that of the conventional method using the nonlinear least-squares fitting. Additionally, this study briefly explains how to use JENDL-5 in the OpenMC calculation and discusses the difference between the calculated and measured α values for the water tank system.

Keywords: neutron decay constant, Monte Carlo method, dynamic mode decomposition, uncertainty due to analytical modeling method

1. INTRODUCTION

For the high-safety and reliable design of nuclear reactors, it is essential to accurately predict k_{eff} through the neutronics calculation in advance. Improving the accuracy of k_{eff} prediction requires a better update of the nuclear data used as the input parameter of a neutronics code. Typically, nuclides with high sensitivities for k_{eff} tend to be preferentially modified for improvement. As clarified in previous studies [1], the uncertainty of the thermal neutron scattering law (TSL) data for light water also affects k_{eff} calculation results in light water moderated reactors. Although further improvement of the TSL data for light water is necessary, it is a challenging issue to selectively improve only the TSL data through data assimilation using critical experiments consisting of various kinds of nuclides. In our previous study to improve the TSL data for light water [2,3], we focused on the neutron decay constant α , which is a unique kinetics parameter and can be measured even in a non-multiplying system. Our study demonstrated the potential to selectively improve the TSL data of light water based on the data assimilation using α values measured in water tank systems [4]. Note, however, that the α eigenvalues

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in our previous study were calculated using an in-house deterministic calculation based on the multigroup S_N method. To carry out the data assimilation using the deterministic method, it is necessary to quantify the uncertainty due to the analytical modeling method, e.g., the numerical error arising from the discretization of spatial meshes, the energy group structure, and the solid angle quadrature. Therefore, our previous study faced the difficulty in evaluating the uncertainty due to the analytical modeling method.

To address the above-mentioned issue, the purposes of this study are as follows: to investigate the α calculation method in a non-multiplying system based on the Monte Carlo method; and to quantify the uncertainty due to the analytical modeling method. As a calculation code for α , this study focused on OpenMC [5]. Since the recent version of OpenMC does not have a function to perform α -eigenvalue calculation, we try applying Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD) [6–10] to estimate the fundamental mode of α -eigenvalue from the OpenMC kinetic calculation. The usefulness of DMD is investigated by comparing the α value with the conventional method using the nonlinear least-squares fitting. Through the OpenMC calculation for the water tank system [4], this study presents the validation of α using OpenMC with JENDL-5 [11], of which ACE-formatted files were generated by the Japanese nuclear data processing code FRENDDY [12] and converted into the HDF5 files for OpenMC. Note that the Monte Carlo calculation inevitably results in the statistical uncertainty of α as the uncertainty due to the analytical modeling method, even if the calculation geometry and the nuclide densities are faithfully modeled. To robustly obtain the α with the statistical uncertainty, we also aim to quantify the statistical uncertainty of α by combining DMD with the random sampling method [10].

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, the numerical theory for α is briefly explained, followed by the explanation of the α -calculation using DMD. Section 3 presents the calculation conditions and procedures of OpenMC for the water tank system, and compares the numerical results of α using DMD with that of least-squares fitting. Finally, concluding remarks are summarized in Section 4.

2. NUMERICAL THEORY

2.1. Kinetic Calculation for α

In this section, we briefly explain the kinetic calculation used to simulate the pulse neutron method [13], and the theoretical basis to calculate the fundamental mode of the α value by combining the OpenMC kinetic calculation and DMD.

Let us assume that a pulsed neutron source is injected into a non-multiplying target system at the time $t = 0$. In this case, the angular neutron flux $\psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, t)$ satisfies the following time-dependent Boltzmann transport equations [14]:

$$\frac{1}{v(E)} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = -\mathbf{A}\psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, t) + \frac{S(\mathbf{r}, E)}{4\pi} \delta(t), \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{A} \equiv \boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \boldsymbol{\nabla} + \Sigma_t(\mathbf{r}, E) - \int_0^\infty dE' \int_{4\pi} d\Omega' \Sigma_s(\mathbf{r}, E' \rightarrow E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}' \rightarrow \boldsymbol{\Omega}), \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{A} denotes the neutron annihilation operator; $S(\mathbf{r}, E)$ means the spatial and energy distribution of the pulsed neutron source; other symbols are the conventional meanings used in reactor physics.

By expanding ψ using ω -eigenfunctions, the analytical solution of Eq. (1) can be obtained as follows:

$$\psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_n \varphi_n(\mathbf{r}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) e^{\omega_n t}, \quad (3)$$

$$f_n = \frac{\int_V dV' \int_0^{\infty} dE' \int_{4\pi} d\Omega' \left(\varphi_n^\dagger(\mathbf{r}', E', \boldsymbol{\Omega}') \frac{S(\mathbf{r}', E')}{4\pi} \right)}{\int_V dV' \int_0^{\infty} dE' \int_{4\pi} d\Omega' \left(\varphi_n^\dagger(\mathbf{r}', E', \boldsymbol{\Omega}') \frac{1}{v(E)} \varphi_n(\mathbf{r}', E', \boldsymbol{\Omega}') \right)}, \quad (4)$$

where f_n denotes the expansion coefficient for the n th mode; the eigenvalue ω_n and the forward eigenfunction $\varphi_n(\mathbf{r}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega})$, and the adjoint eigenfunction $\varphi_n^\dagger(\mathbf{r}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega})$ satisfy the following ω -eigenvalue equations:

$$\mathbf{A} \varphi_n(\mathbf{r}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) = -\frac{\omega_n}{v(E)} \varphi_n(\mathbf{r}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}), \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{A}^\dagger \varphi_n^\dagger(\mathbf{r}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) = -\frac{\omega_n}{v(E)} \varphi_n^\dagger(\mathbf{r}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}), \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{A}^\dagger \equiv -\boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \boldsymbol{\nabla} + \Sigma_t(\mathbf{r}, E) - \int_0^{\infty} dE' \int_{4\pi} d\Omega' \Sigma_s(\mathbf{r}, E \rightarrow E', \boldsymbol{\Omega} \rightarrow \boldsymbol{\Omega}'). \quad (7)$$

Note that $0 > \omega_0 \geq \omega_1 \geq \omega_2 \geq \dots$ in a non-multiplying system.

Let us assume that a kinetic calculation simulating the pulse neutron method is carried out using the Monte Carlo method. Then, the tallies of total neutron flux for N_M spatial regions are arranged into a one-dimensional vector $\vec{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_M}$. Based on Eq. (3), the time variation of $\vec{x}(t)$ obtained by the Monte Carlo kinetic calculation can be expressed by the following sum of exponential functions $e^{\omega_i t}$:

$$\vec{x}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_M} C_i \vec{\phi}_i e^{\omega_i t}, \quad (8)$$

where C_i denotes the expansion coefficient for i th component; $\vec{\phi}_i$ denotes the eigenvector corresponding to the spatial distribution. In this study, we used the symmetrical tally region in the OpenMC calculation in order to reduce the contributions due to higher-order mode components. Thereby, we expect that the fundamental mode of the eigenfunction is dominant in the calculated tallies.

2.2. Dynamic Mode Decomposition

Let us consider that neutrons are successively counted by N_T time steps of time interval Δt in each of the N_M spatial regions. The discrete time-series data is arranged into a matrix $\mathbf{X} \equiv (\vec{x}_1 \vec{x}_2 \dots \vec{x}_{N_T}) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_M \times N_T}$. The DMD assumes that two slicing matrices $\mathbf{X}_{1:N_T-1}$ and $\mathbf{X}_{2:N_T}$ satisfies the following relationship using the time evolution matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_M \times N_M}$ [6]:

$$\mathbf{A} \mathbf{X}_{1:N_T-1} \approx \mathbf{X}_{2:N_T}, \quad (9)$$

where the matrix $\mathbf{X}_{i:j} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_M \times (j-i+1)}$ is constructed by taking from the i th row to the j th column vectors from the original data matrix \mathbf{X} . The time evolution matrix \mathbf{A} transforms each time-step data into the next time-step data.

In DMD, the time evolution matrix \mathbf{A} can be estimated by the following data-driven manner. First, $\mathbf{X}_{1:N_T-1}$ is decomposed into three matrices using singular value decomposition (SVD) as follows:

$$\mathbf{X}_{1:N_T-1} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^T, \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_M \times r}$ and $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{(N_T-1) \times r}$ are semi-unitary matrices consisting of the left and right singular vectors, respectively; $\mathbf{\Sigma} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$ is a diagonal matrix where the diagonal elements correspond to singular values; r is the rank of the matrix \mathbf{A} ; and the superscript T means the transpose. Using Eq. (10), the pseudo-inverse matrix $\mathbf{X}_{1:N_T-1}^+$ [15] can be obtained by

$$\mathbf{X}_{1:N_T-1}^+ = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{U}^T, \quad (11)$$

where the superscript -1 indicates the inverse of a matrix. By multiplying both sides of Eq. (9) by $\mathbf{X}_{1:N_T-1}^+$ of Eq. (11) from the right, the time evolution matrix \mathbf{A} can be expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{X}_{2:N_T}\mathbf{V}\mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{U}^T. \quad (12)$$

In the exact DMD [7], the matrix \mathbf{A} is projected onto \mathbf{U} to obtain the reduced order matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{U}^T\mathbf{A}\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{U}^T\mathbf{X}_{2:N_T}\mathbf{V}\mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1}, \quad (13)$$

By applying the eigenvalue decomposition to $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ estimated by Eq. (13), the eigenvalues μ_i and the eigenvectors $\vec{w}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times 1}$ of $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ are obtained for each mode ($i = 1, 2, \dots, r$). By reprojecting the matrix consisting of the eigenvectors $\mathbf{W} = (\vec{w}_1 \vec{w}_2 \dots \vec{w}_r) \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$, the eigenvectors for the original matrix \mathbf{A} can be estimated as follows:

$$\mathbf{\Phi} = (\vec{\phi}_1 \vec{\phi}_2 \dots \vec{\phi}_r) = \mathbf{X}_{2:N_T}\mathbf{V}\mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1}\mathbf{W}\text{diag}(1/\mu_i) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_M \times r}, \quad (14)$$

$$\text{diag}(1/\mu_i) \equiv \begin{pmatrix} 1/\mu_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 1/\mu_2 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 1/\mu_r \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}, \quad (15)$$

Consequently, the time-series data $\vec{x}(t)$ by an OpenMC kinetic calculation, which simulates a virtual pulsed neutron method, can be expanded using the exponential terms:

$$\vec{x}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^r C_i \vec{\phi}_i \exp(\omega_i t), \quad (16)$$

$$\vec{C} = (C_1 \ C_2 \ \dots \ C_r)^T = \mathbf{\Phi}^+ \vec{x}_1, \quad (17)$$

$$\omega_i = \frac{\ln(\mu_i)}{\Delta t}, \quad (18)$$

where C_i and ω_i are the amplitude (or the expansion coefficient) and the exponential growth constant for the i th mode ($\omega_1 > \omega_2 > \dots$), respectively. Note that the neutron decay constant α for the fundamental mode corresponds to the slowest negative constant, and the sign of α is opposite to that of ω_1 , i.e.,

$$\alpha = -\omega_1 = -\frac{\ln(\mu_1)}{\Delta t}. \quad (19)$$

3. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

3.1. Calculation Conditions

Pulse neutron experiments [4] were previously conducted on some water tank systems of different sizes to measure the neutron decay constant α . In this study, the smallest water tank system, which has the largest geometric buckling (i.e., the highest neutron leakage fraction), was selected because the α value for the smallest system is highly sensitive to the thermal neutron scattering law. The kinetic calculation for α was carried out using OpenMC [5]. The calculation geometry is shown in Figure 1. As shown in the left figure, the light water is covered by the 1 mm-thick aluminum plates on all sides except for the top surface. For this calculation geometry, the neutron flux was tallied as a spatiotemporal matrix using ten equally spaced regions ($N_M = 10$), as shown in the right figure. In this study, the rank r in the SVD is equal to the number of regions (N_M).

Figure 1. Calculation geometry.

Table I. Nuclide density for each material.

Material	Temperature (K)	Nuclide	Nuclide density (atoms/barn/cm)
H ₂ O	283.15	¹ H	$6.68280883425465 \times 10^{-2}$
		² H	$7.68611406251003 \times 10^{-6}$
		¹⁶ O	$3.33366817623397 \times 10^{-2}$
		¹⁷ O	$1.26987971467557 \times 10^{-5}$
		¹⁸ O	$6.85066688180242 \times 10^{-5}$
Al	293.6	²⁷ Al	$6.03072515174787 \times 10^{-2}$

Table I summarizes the temperature and nuclide density for each region. These input parameters were set to match the experimental conditions in Ref. [4] as closely as possible, and are consistent with those used in our previous study [3]. The nuclear data of all nuclides and the thermal neutron scattering law were taken from JENDL-5 [11]. In order to convert the nuclear data into the HDF5 files available in OpenMC, the ACE-formatted files of JENDL-5 were generated using FRENDY [12]. In the FRENDY calculations, we set the temperature conditions to be as close as possible to the experimental values. Finally, the HDF5 files of JENDL-5 were converted using the Python module of “openmc.data” from the generated ACE-formatted files.

In the virtual pulsed neutron simulation with OpenMC, the neutron source was modeled by a delta function in time ($0 \leq t \leq 10^{-10}$ s) and a uniform distribution within the water region. In order to easily extract the fundamental mode of α , the energy spectrum of the neutron source was given by a Maxwellian distribution at the room temperature. In the fixed-source kinetic calculation, total neutron histories were 1,000 batches \times 1,000,000 histories/batch. The time step width of the neutron flux was set to $\Delta t = 2.5 \times 10^{-7}$ s, and the total number of time steps was set to $N_T = 400$, i.e., the total measurement time of the virtual pulsed neutron method was $N_T \times \Delta t = 0.0001$ s. To compare the α value using DMD, the α value was also analyzed using the conventional method, i.e., the nonlinear least-squares fitting [16] for the time-series data of neutron flux within the entire water region. Furthermore, to evaluate the statistical uncertainty due to the Monte Carlo method, the random sampling method [10] was applied in the α estimations by DMD and the least-squares fitting. Here, we approximated that the OpenMC result of neutron flux follows a normal distribution, and the statistical error was used as the standard deviation (1σ) without consideration of correlation between flux tallies at different time steps. The random sampling method was performed without the correlation between the neutron fluxes at different times, and the sample size was 10,000.

3.2. Numerical Results

Figure 2 shows the variations in α values with respect to the different masking time using the conventional method (fitting) and the DMD approach. In Figure 2, the error bar represents the statistical uncertainty of α (shown as 1σ) estimated by the random sampling method. The masking time on the horizontal axis indicates the time interval removed from the beginning of the kinetic calculation. The marked point corresponds to the minimum relative error of α for both methods. For validation, the dashed line indicates the experimental result of α ($\alpha_{\text{exp}} = 44683 \pm 182 \text{ s}^{-1}$) presented in Ref. [4].

Figure 2 shows that the α values calculated by both methods agree within the statistical uncertainties as the masking time increases. In the conventional method, there is a large systematic bias in the calculated α unless the masking time is sufficiently large. This bias seems to be due to the higher order mode components. On the other hand, compared with the conventional method, the α value by DMD is closer to α_{exp} with fewer masking time. Therefore, we confirmed the effectiveness of DMD to calculate the fundamental mode of α .

Note, however, that the converged values of α by both methods do not agree with the experimental value α_{exp} within the ranges of measurement uncertainty and the statistical uncertainty due to the analytical modeling method. The reason for this discrepancy seems to be due to the uncertainty of TSL data for the light water, because the TSL data-induced uncertainty (1σ) of α was approximately 1800 s^{-1} as discussed in our preliminary analysis [3]. As a future research topic, we expect that the TSL

data can be improved using the data assimilation to reduce the systematic bias between the experimental and calculated α values.

Figure 2. Comparison of α values by least-squares fitting and DMD with 1σ statistical uncertainty.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the applicability of the DMD to the OpenMC kinetic calculation was investigated to estimate the fundamental mode of α with the uncertainty due to the analytical modeling method, i.e., statistical uncertainty of the Monte Carlo method. Through the comparison of the α values obtained by the conventional fitting method and DMD for the smallest water tank system, the usefulness of DMD was confirmed. Although there is a systematic bias between the calculated and measured α values, we guess that there is room for improvement in the TSL data of the light water.

One of the future research topics is further investigation into the usefulness of other DMD methods (e.g., “optimized DMD”) to robustly extract the fundamental mode of α . Another research topic is the development of a more rigorous statistical uncertainty quantification method that accounts for the covariance between neutron flux tallies at different time steps. Furthermore, we will investigate the uncertainty quantification due to the TSL data of light water based on the CAB model, followed by the data assimilation using experimental α values.

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